

The *Arion lusitanicus* complex (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Arionidae) in Cantabria (North of the Iberian peninsula)

El complejo de *Arion lusitanicus* (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Arionidae) en Cantabria (Norte de la Península Ibérica)

Carlos GARRIDO, José CASTILLEJO, y Javier IGLESIAS

ABSTRACT

With specimens collected in Cantabria *Arion fuliginus* is reported for the first time outside Portugal, and information on a still undescribed species of the *A. lusitanicus* complex is given.

RESUMEN

Ejemplares recogidos en Cantabria permiten citar por primera vez *Arion fuliginus* fuera de Portugal y dar noticia de una nueva especie del complejo *A. lusitanicus*.

KEY WORDS: Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Arionidae, *Arion*, taxonomy, Iberian peninsula.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Arionidae, *Arion*, taxonomía, Península Ibérica.

INTRODUCTION

With middle or great-sized *Arion* of the Portuguese fauna several malacologists (Morelet, Mabilie, Pollonera, and Simroth) established a number of nominal species in the last century. Very frequently, the descriptions of these taxa rest solely on external characters and discrepancies among the authors led to reciprocal taxonomic emendations and continuous synonymization.

With material from Portugal the following middle or great-sized *Arion* species were described, which commonly exhibit dark stripes on the back and, when illustrated, a small genital atrium

and enlarged free-oviduct: *Arion fuliginus* Morelet, 1845, *A. fuscatus* Morelet, 1845 [non Férussac, 1819], *A. pascalianus* Mabilie, 1868, *A. lusitanicus* Mabilie, 1868, *A. dasilvae* Pollonera, 1887, and *A. nobrei* Pollonera, 1889. With the exception of *Arion lusitanicus* Mabilie, 1868, none of the above-mentioned nominal taxa has been used for the arionid fauna outside the Iberian peninsula, and only recently it has been pointed out (ALTENA, 1955; DAVIES, 1987) that within Mabilie's nominal taxon a number of different species may be comprised (such as *Arion flagellus* Collinge, 1893).

Also, due to the lack of specialists concentrating on the Portuguese fauna, until recently only the nominal taxon *Arion lusitanicus* had been regularly employed in the Iberian peninsula, and the other names of the group fell into oblivion (CASTILLEJO AND RODRÍGUEZ, 1991). Nevertheless, in 1990 appears Rodríguez's study on the slugs of Portugal (doctoral thesis), which, together with a revision of the genus *Arion* in Portugal (CASTILLEJO AND RODRÍGUEZ, 1993), clarifies the taxonomic problem of the *Arion lusitanicus* group. In these works several forms allied to *A. lusitanicus* are distinguished, and the nominal

species *A. fuliginus* and *A. nobrei* are rehabilitated for taxonomical usage.

Our sampling work in Cantabria has yielded a series of specimens that can be ascribed to two forms related to the *Arion lusitanicus* group. One of them, found in the northern part of the region, shows similar features to those of *A. fuliginus*, as re-described by CASTILLEJO AND RODRÍGUEZ (1990), and so constitutes the first citation of the species outside Portugal. In addition we have collected in various localities of Cantabria a novel form of the complex, which will be provisionally termed *Arion* sp. Next, data on these two forms of *Arion lusitanicus* s. l. are presented.

SYSTEMATICS

Arion fuliginus Morelet, 1845 (Fig. 1)

Collection sites: Argoños, 30TVP61: 6-XI-89, 1 adult specimen. Santoña, 30TVP61: 6-XI-89, 6 adult specimens + 1 juvenile.

Description: Animals of 3-6 cm long (on average, preserved adult specimens measure 4.8 cm long). With black or dark brown dorsum, along which two lateral grey stripes run. These stripes extend from behind the mantle, back to the caudal end, where they join. The skin tubercles are relatively small. Sole whitish. In the specimens preserved in alcohol lateral stripes may vanish and the sole, which is smooth due to the lack of striation, normally turns to greyish-yellow or greenish.

The posterior free-oviduct (Fig. 1A) is long and receives the insertion of one branch of the genital retractor muscle; the other branch joins the region between the spermatheca duct and the bursa copulatrix. The anterior free-oviduct is very thick and long and contains a V-shaped ligula (Fig. 1B), with its vertex pointing to the atrium. The spermatheca duct is of variable length and joins an ovoid, sometimes tapering, bursa copulatrix. The epiphallus is black-pigmented on its anterior portion, in the vicinity of a conspicuous ring-shaped outgrowth. The vas deferens is a little longer than half the length of the epiphallus, being the mean

length ratio of vas deferens to epiphallus 0.58. On average, the epiphallus measures 18.9 mm (interval: 16.3-23.4), whilst the vas deferens is 10.9 mm long (interval: 8.5-14).

The lower atrium is relatively big and the upper one exhibits a remarkable internal structure (Fig. 1C). This is a papilla situated close to the entry of the spermatheca duct into atrium, continued in finger-like extensions towards the bursa and originated from the ligula.

Secondary muscles of the genital system are a retentor, which is inserted on the atrial end of the anterior free-oviduct, and a muscle joining the ring-shaped structure of the anterior epiphallus.

Discussion: The morphological features of this form, both external and anatomical, accord well with the redescription of *Arion fuliginus* by RODRÍGUEZ (1990) and CASTILLEJO AND RODRÍGUEZ (1993), based on Portuguese specimens. Only in the colouration there are little differences: in the populations studied here no orange-coloured individuals were observed.

Figure 1. *Arion fuliginus* from Argoños (Cantabria). A: reproductive system (hermaphrodite duct cut off); B: ligula within anterior free-oviduct; C: folds within upper atrium. Scale bars 2 mm.

Figura 1. *Arion fuliginus* de Argoños (Cantabria). A: aparato genital (conducto hermafrodita retirado); B: lígula en la porción oviductal anterior; C: pliegues en el atrio superior. Escalas 2 mm.

It would be interesting to know the spermatophore of this form from Cantabria in order to make a comparison with that of the Portuguese form (20-30 mm

long), as well as the copulation (as far as Portuguese populations are concerned, with continuous clock-wise turning of the pair).

Figure 2. *Arion* sp. from Cantabria. A-C: copulatory organs, ligula within anterior free-oviduct and spermatophore of a specimen from Puerto de los Tornos; D: five stages of copulation (Saja forest). Scale bars 2 mm.

Figura 2. *Arion* sp. de Cantabria. A-C: aparato genital, lígula en la porción oviductal anterior y espermatóforo de un espécimen de Puerto de los Tornos; D: cinco estados de cópula (Bosque de Saja). Escalas 2 mm.

Arion sp. (Fig. 2)

Collection sites: Bárcena Mayor, 30TVN07: 15-VI-87: 2 adult specimens. Fuente De, 30TUN57: 10-VI-87, 2 adult specimens. Puerto de los Tornos, 30TVN67: 27-IX-91, 4 adult specimens. Saja, 30TUN97: 14-VI-87, 2 adult specimens, and 28-IX-91, 4 adult specimens (with copulation and spermatophores!). Terán, 30TUN99: 13-VI-87, 2 adult specimens.

Description: Slugs of great size: preserved adults measure from 4.3 to 7.5 cm long (mean length= 6.1). The dorsum and mantle are black or light-brown, neck white, and tentacles, black. The sole is tripartite, with two lateral grey bands and a whitish central one. The skin tubercles are very long and sometimes have an undulated shape.

The anterior free-oviduct (Fig. 2A) is very long and contains a V-shaped ligula (Fig. 2B) with the vertex near the atrium. In the upper atrium, coming from the ligula, there are folds that form a structure similar to that present in *A. fuliginus*. Epiphallus longer than vas deferens, but the difference between them is not so great as in *A. fuliginus* (mean ratio vd/ep= 0.87): on average the length of epiphallus is 26.2 mm (range: 22-36) and that of vas deferens, 21.1 mm (range: 19.3-28.9). In some specimens the spermatheca duct and the epiphallus run into a small expansion of the upper atrium. The anterior end of epiphallus shows a ring-shaped outgrowth and is occasionally pigmented. The spermatheca duct is relatively long. The bursa copulatrix is ovoid and of great size.

Copulation and spermatophore: In Saja, at 19:30 of a day in September a pair

was discovered at copula on the grass growing at the sides of a forest pathway. The individuals, one black and the other brown, followed one another in circle, bending in a C-shape and licking the partner's tail. The movement was clock-wise (Fig. 2D) and it took them 8 minutes to complete one turn. The genital mass was everted and each individual placed its ligula against the partner's body: one ligula rested on the upper dorsum, whilst the other leaned against the side. Tentacles remained retracted. While the exchange of spermatophores took place, the odontophores and radulae could be seen as they were employed in scraping and even biting the dorsum, neck and ligula of the partner. After a time the rotation speed diminishes, the individuals contract and begin to retract the genital mass, while the tentacles are evaginated. Finally, the partners separate without crossing and one of them follows the other licking the trail of caudal mucus left.

Within the spermatheca, upper atrium and anterior free oviduct of both specimens discovered in copulation spermatophores were found. One of them is 51 mm long and the other, 61 mm. They are cylindrical (Fig. 3C), and are provided with a helically arranged crest of denticles.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALTEÑA, C. O. VAN R., 1955. Notes sur limaces, 3. Sur la présence en France d'*Arion lusitanicus* Mabille. *Journal of Conchology*, 95 (3): 89-99.
- CASTILLEJO, J. AND RODRÍGUEZ, T., 1991. *Babosas de la Península Ibérica y Baleares. Inventario crítico, citas y mapas de distribución*. Monografías da Universidade de Santiago. Santiago de Compostela. 211 pp.
- CASTILLEJO, J. AND RODRÍGUEZ, T., 1993. Portuguese slugs. Revision of the genus *Arion* Férussac, 1819. *Graellsia*, 49: 5-37.
- DAVIES, S. M., 1987. *Arion flagellus* Collinge and *A. lusitanicus* Mabille in the British isles: a morphological, biological and taxonomic investigation. *Journal of Conchology*, 32: 339-354.
- RODRÍGUEZ, T., 1990. *Babosas de Portugal*. Ph. D. Thesis. University of Santiago de Compostela. 408 pp.

Recibido el 17-XII-1992

Aceptado el 18-VI-1993